

Attempting Exomoon Detection and Constraining Moon Radii with TESS Data of LHS1140 System

LOGAN WILSON¹

¹*Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics
60 Garden Street
Cambridge, MA 02138*

ABSTRACT

Terrestrial moons have yet to be discovered outside of the solar system. Here, we present an analysis of the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) data of transits of LHS 1140 b and LHS 1140 c to determine whether these planetary transit events also contain secondary transit events of terrestrial exomoons. To make this determination, we compared the χ^2 value of a transit model for a lone-planet transit event to that of a transit model with both a planetary transit and a secondary exomoon transit. For the single transit of LHS 1140 b, we determined the probability of the null-hypothesis to be $p = 0.672$, indicating that the exomoon transit model does not attain statistical significance over the lone-planet transit model and that we have no evidence for the presence of an exomoon. Based on the noise of the data, we are able to rule out all exomoons greater than 0.51 planet radii (0.88 Earth radii). We conducted an equivalent analysis on six transits of LHS 1140 c, obtaining a minimum probability for the null hypothesis of $p = .664$, again failing to reveal an exomoon. Just as before, we can constrain the maximum radius of an undetected exomoon, placing this maximum value at 0.66 planet radii (0.85 Earth radii). We also conducted multiple successful injection and recovery tests on simulated data with slightly higher precision than the TESS data, with $\sigma = 0.001$ instead of 0.005, for simulated exomoon systems with the same planet-moon radius ratio as that of Earth and its moon, where $R_m/R_\oplus = 0.27$. These repeated successes increase our confidence in our null results in our analysis of the LHS 1140 exoplanets, but give hope of successful detection of an exomoon in the future within transit events of other systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The detection of an exomoon is one of the most interesting challenges at the forefront of modern astronomy. Based on our solar system sample, we expect exomoons to be abundant, but they are incredibly difficult to detect due to their small size. The largest moon in our solar system, Ganymede, would generate a transit depth of roughly 14 parts-per-million (ppm), which falls below the limiting precision of the TESS and Kepler missions (at 50 ppm and 30 ppm, respectively). This transit depth even pushes the limits of the James Webb Space Telescope, which has a limiting precision of approximately 5 ppm. Our moon, with a transit depth of roughly 6 ppm, would be right at the detection limit of JWST. Evidently, the detection of an exomoon transit pushes modern observational technology to its farthest limits.

The search for exomoons has not been entirely unfruitful, though, as a few candidates have been identified. Two prominent exomoon host candidates, Kepler-1708 b and Kepler-1625 b, are theorized to have exomoons of 2.6 Earth radii and 4 Earth radii, respectively (Kipping et al. 2022). These unconfirmed exomoons, expected to be much larger than any of the terrestrial planets within our solar system, lie as outliers relative to our current sample of moons, and, if confirmed, would require us to adjust our expectations for what exomoons may exist.

To orient our project, let us first discuss the motivations and challenges of exomoon detection, the different possible orientations of exomoon transits, and the focus of our study, LHS 1140.

1.1. *Exomoons and Habitability*

The Earth/moon system is unique within the solar system due to the moon's unusually large radius and mass relative to the earth; none of the other planets in the solar system have moons that compare in relative size. Our moon isn't the largest in absolute size the solar system, but it is the only large moon around a terrestrial planet and the only large

moon to form inside the ice line. The uniqueness of our moon within the solar system might lead one to question if a large moon might have an effect on its companion planet’s habitability. Mechanisms have been proposed to explain how a large exomoon may impact exoplanet habitability; A leading theory is that a large exomoon would help to stabilize the obliquity of the planet’s rotation, promoting climate stability (Kane 2017). Further, a large exomoon could have a tidal impact on the planet, promoting the pooling of liquid water (Kane 2017). Both of these effects are directly observed on Earth and have been seen to positively influence the habitability of our home.

Despite the positive impact of a large moon on the habitability of its companion, it is believed that a moonless Earth would not necessarily preclude life, and therefore an exoplanet could likewise be habitable without an exomoon (Kane 2017). In other words, current consensus indicates that exomoon presence and exoplanet habitability are not mutually exclusive. Consequently, when considering the relationship between exomoons and habitability, the impact of exomoons on the habitability of the exoplanet is frequently a secondary consideration to the habitability of the exomoon itself.

Most observed exoplanets that are located in their star’s habitable zones are gas giants rather than terrestrial planets. Therefore, some estimates indicate that the exomoons of these giant exoplanets could actually be the most numerous population of habitable worlds (Heller et al. 2014). Exomoons around giant exoplanets are particularly appealing because they are more likely to be rich in volatiles (Dobos et al. 2021). Similar systems can be seen within our own solar system; Europa, Ganymede, Titan, and Enceladus are all suspected to have liquid water, a stable source of energy, and a steady supply of nutrients, and therefore meet the basic requirements for life (Heller et al. 2014). All of these moons are interesting locations to check for life, and would be even more likely to be habitable if their host planets were in the stellar habitable zone. Exomoons are fascinating options to consider as potential hosts of life for the reasons outlined above, and their expected abundance further compounds this appeal. Based on our knowledge of the solar system planets, terrestrial exomoons may outnumber terrestrial exoplanets, and water-hosting terrestrial exomoons may also outnumber water-hosting terrestrial exoplanets (Heller et al. 2014).

Exomoons have immense implications on our attempt to predict the chance of life existing outside of the solar system; they both positively influence the habitability of their host exoplanets and serve as potential hosts of life themselves. Consequently, confirmation of the first exomoon and the following attempt to characterize exomoon frequency may significantly alter our perspective regarding the probability of life existing outside of our solar system.

1.2. Exomoons Reveal Planetary Characteristics and History

There are many different mechanisms that could lead to the formation of an exomoon. Perhaps the most likely of these processes is condensation out of the accretion disc around a protoplanet, as simulated by Lunine & Stevenson (1982) and observed by Benisty et al. (2021). Also worth consideration, however, are the possibilities of exomoon capture or exomoon formation following a large collision (Heller et al. 2014). We can observe evidence of these collision and capture events in the solar system. Earth’s moon formed as a result of a collision, and Neptune’s moon Triton as a result of capture (Hartmann & Davis (1975); McCord (1966)). Since most exoplanets are between the sizes of Earth and Neptune, we can conclude that exomoon capture or collision are possible events for many exoplanets. If we were to detect an exomoon and conduct recurring observations on it (allowing us to estimate exoplanet transit timing variations and transit duration variation values), we could estimate its radius, mass, density, orbital period, and orbital distance. These parameters could provide insight into the formation story of the exomoon, and also about the conditions of the protoplanetary disc at the time of the exoplanet’s formation.

Exomoons’ ability to provide insight into the formation conditions of the protoplanetary disc could provide insight into the exoplanet radius valley. This phenomena describes the observed peaks of exoplanet frequency at $R \sim 1.5R_{\oplus}$ and $R \sim 2.7R_{\oplus}$ and valley at $R \sim 2R_{\oplus}$ (Venturini et al. 2020). The increased frequency of exoplanets around $R \sim 2.7R_{\oplus}$, sometimes referred to as ‘puffy earths,’ could be explained either by inward migration of gas giants or by gas accretion of terrestrial exoplanets; there is much debate between these two competing theories. Observations of exomoons around one of these ‘puffy earths’ could resolve this debate; if the exomoon is rocky, then the exoplanet likely accreted its own gas, whereas if the moon is icy, then the exoplanet likely migrated inwards from behind the ice line.

Exomoons could also provide information about their host planet’s core composition, as the timescale of moon orbital evolution depends directly on the intensity of dissipation in the planet’s interior (Dobos et al. 2021). An exoplanet with intense energy dissipation would be able to efficiently transfer angular momentum to its satellite, causing it to migrate outwards until it escapes the exoplanet’s gravitational influence. Consequently, if we observe a large exomoon

in a stable orbit, we would be able to place an upper bound on the intensity of energy dissipation within the exoplanet’s mantle. These dissipation rates could provide insight into the relationship between the exoplanet’s core and its mantle, meaning that exomoons could help us to metaphorically x-ray their host exoplanets.

Further, detection and characterization of an exomoon would allow us to predict the future of the exoplanet system that it resides in. All exoplanets have a characteristic synchronous orbital distance, where a moon’s orbital period would equal the planet’s rotational period. Inside this radius, the moon would begin to migrate inwards until decomposing upon reaching the exoplanet’s Roche limit. Outside this radius, it would begin to drift outwards (Dobos et al. 2021). Therefore, if we know the exoplanet’s rotation period and an exomoon’s orbital distance, we can predict the future movement of its moon towards or away from its exoplanet. Conversely, if we could infer the radial movement of the exomoon relative to its exoplanet, we could model the rotational period of the exoplanet.

1.3. Difficulty of Exomoon Detection

Moons are expected to be a common consequence of the formation of planetary systems, but they have yet to be detected. In order for a moon to be detected, it first must exist in a stable state and then we must observe it. Let us first consider the frequency of stable exomoons. This frequency will be dependent upon two factors: their formation rates and their survival rates (Dobos et al. 2021). Exomoon formation rates are quite uncertain (as none have been observed outside of the solar system), but simulation results yield a reasonably high exomoon occurrence rate of around 10% around smaller terrestrial exoplanets (Barr 2016). We would also expect a noticeably higher rate for larger gas giant exoplanets based on our solar system sample. Moon survival rates are strongly correlated with their planet’s orbital period, and, according to Dobos et al. (2021), are usually greater than 50% for exoplanets with the median exoplanet orbital period of 11.8 days (Makarov & Efroimsky 2023). With neither formation nor survivability expected to be limiting, the lack of exomoon detection becomes an even more perplexing phenomena.

If exomoons are expected to be both forming and surviving at a high rate, then the limiting factor on our detection of exomoons must be observation, not the exomoons’ existence. Since we are only searching for exomoons in systems which are already known to be transiting and exomoons would likely be close to their companions on co-planar orbits, there are likely few non-transiting exomoons around transiting exoplanets.

Transit alignment, however, can still be a limiting factor for observing exoplanets. For an exomoon transit to be visible, the exomoon must not be directly in line with the exoplanet, as in this case the exomoon would not be blocking any additional light. The chance of this alignment is dependent upon the exomoon’s orbital distance and the exoplanet’s radius: larger orbital distances increase visible transit probability, while larger planet radii decrease visible transit probability. The probability of a moon being hidden in a particular transit can be roughly estimated by dividing the radius of the planet by the orbital distance of the moon: $p = R/a$. More accurately, though, applying some basic trigonometry, we would expect it to be:

$$p = \frac{\arccos\left(-\frac{R_p}{a}\right) - \arccos\left(\frac{R_p}{a}\right)}{\pi} \quad (1)$$

Now, if we assume that an exomoon is equally likely to be at any radius between its Roche Limit and its Hill Sphere (the upper and lower constraints on exomoons orbital distance, which are discussed in greater detail in the following section) and that its density is equal to that of its companion, then we would calculate that the probability of an exomoon being oriented directly in front of or behind its companion to be:

$$p = \frac{\int_{3^{\frac{1}{3}}R_p}^{R_H} \left(\arccos\left(-\frac{R_p}{a}\right) - \arccos\left(\frac{R_p}{a}\right) \right) da}{\pi \left(R_H/R_p - 3^{\frac{1}{3}} \right)} \quad (2)$$

This probability comes out to approximately $p = 0.0054$ for Jupiter, $p = 0.014$ for Earth, $p = 0.052$ for LHS 1140 b, and $p = 0.14$ for LHS 1140 c. Even in the worst case scenario, where an exomoon is at the exoplanet’s Roche Limit (as close as it can be), $p = 0.488$ that it would be hidden in front of or behind the exoplanet. It is also worth noting that this probability of unfavorable alignment is only for one single transit event - by observing multiple transits of

a single exoplanet, the chance of repeatedly encountering this invisible exomoon alignment decreases exponentially. Clearly, this transit alignment factor is not primarily responsible for our lack of detected exomoons.

The largest bottleneck on exomoon detection seems to be instrumental limitations. The three telescopes with the greatest possibility of exomoon detection currently appear to be TESS, JWST, and Kepler. Each one, however, comes with its own limitations.

TESS is designed to observe nearby, bright stars. Consequently, as outlined by [Ricker et al. \(2010\)](#), it struggles at analyzing low-mass stars such as LHS 1140 which are most favorable for both exomoon existence (due to the exoplanets having a larger gravitational effect relative to their star) and exomoon detection (due to the exomoon generating larger transit depths). TESS also generally has a short temporal baseline for a given star, with a sector length of about 27 days, meaning that it may struggle to identify long-term transit patterns, such as transit timing variations (TTVs) or transit duration variations (TDVs), which are currently both required to characterize an exomoon's mass and orbital parameters ([Kipping 2014](#)).

The JWST also comes with limitations, primarily that observational time is challenging to obtain. Therefore, it would be difficult to observe multiple transit events of an exomoon. JWST would be incredibly effective at identifying a single exomoon transit event due to its superb signal-to-noise ratio, but would not be useful in constraining the mass, orbital period, or orbital radius of the exomoon, due to the competitiveness of obtaining multiple observations.

Kepler may have greatest chance of exomoon characterization due to its high signal-to-noise ratio, its focus on low-mass stars, and its long-spanning observations. Even with Kepler, though, only about one sixth of its star observations would have sufficient signal-to-noise to detect both TTV and TDV effects for Earth-mass moons with a 25% recovery rate ([Kipping 2014](#)). This means that, even for the best observing option available right now, we would only be able to characterize properties for roughly 1 out of 25 stable, transiting, earth-mass exomoons. Kepler is also weak relative to other telescopes in terms of its small field of view; with a field of view of only 10 deg x 10 deg, there are simply few bright, small stars observed by Kepler.

Considering the limitations on exomoon existence, stability, transit visibility, and instrumental capabilities, the lack of exomoon detection becomes less surprising. Despite these challenges, there are numerous invaluable scientific motivations for attempting exomoon detection which justify pursuing this difficult task.

1.4. Dynamical Possibilities of Exomoons

Before we begin searching through data and attempting to identify exomoon transits, let us first discuss what possible transit events we might detect. The maximum radius at which an exomoon could be gravitationally bound to its planet instead of to its star is given by exoplanet's Hill Sphere radius, as outlined by [Limbach et al. \(2021\)](#), where:

$$R_H = a_p \left(\frac{M_p}{3 \cdot M_\star} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (3)$$

It is also worth discussing the internal bound on an exomoon's orbital distance, which is given by the Roche Limit ([Kipping 2009](#)). The Roche Limit is defined as:

$$R_{Roche} = R_p \left(3 \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_m} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (4)$$

This parameter is a very important physical constraint on the system, as it dictates how close an exomoon can get to its host exoplanet before being torn apart by tidal forces. Despite its physical importance, it does not impact our calculations of the offset between exoplanet and exomoon transit timing, as exomoons may appear very close to (or in front of or behind) their exoplanet from our side-on perspective due to their location within their orbit.

It follows, then, that the greatest possible time offset between the planetary transit and the moon transit would be given by the Hill Sphere radius divided by the exoplanet's orbital velocity:

$$\Delta T_{max} = \frac{R_H}{v_p} = \frac{a_p \left(\frac{M_p}{3 \cdot M_\star} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\frac{2\pi \cdot a_p}{P}} = \frac{P}{2\pi} \left(\frac{M_p}{3 \cdot M_\star} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (5)$$

Any values of ΔT between $-\Delta T_{max}$ and ΔT_{max} , then, are possible values for our transit time offset. For many exoplanets, the value of ΔT_{max} exceeds the length of their transit. LHS 1140 b, for example, has $\Delta T_{max} = 192.3$

182 minutes, which is greater than its $T_{transit} = 118.3$ minutes. Consequently, it is possible for an exomoon that is bound
 183 to an exoplanet to have its own distinct transit event.

184 With this in mind, let us take a look at some examples of dynamically possible exomoon transit events:

Figure 1. Above, we see two simulated exomoon and exoplanet transit events for LHS 1140 b and an exomoon with a quarter of its radius. In the first panel, the moon is leading the planet from a great enough distance to generate two separate transits. These transit events are the easiest to detect, as there is no interference between the objects' signals. In the second panel, the exomoon is only leading the planet by 50 minutes, leading to an overlapping transit. These overlapping events are slightly harder to detect, as the additional dip in flux from the moon transit can be falsely interpreted as a larger exoplanet radius.

185 Or, in the case where ΔT of the exomoon transit is near 0, the exomoon's transit can be fully hidden:

Figure 2. If the star, planet, and moon are all aligned from our perspective, then the exomoon will not reduce observed stellar flux, and there will be no evidence of an exomoon transit. These events would be common for exomoons in systems with larger stars, as large stars decrease the Hill Sphere radius and overlapping transits are far more likely for exomoons orbiting close to their exoplanet. The equation to estimate the probability of this transit orientation are given in [Section 1.3](#)

186 With some exposure to the possible alignments of exomoon transit events, let us take a look at the LHS 1140 system,
 187 the target of our search for exomoons.

188 1.5. LHS 1140 System

189 Our research focus in this project is the LHS 1140 system, which is known to host two exoplanets. This system mid
 190 M-dwarf system is quite close to us, which is part of the reason that it is such an appealing candidate to study ([Ment
 191 et al. 2019](#)). The parameters of this system are outlined in the table below, with credit to [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#) and [Gaia
 192 Collaboration et al. \(2018\)](#).

	Stellar Parameters	
Distance (pc)	14.993 ± 0.015	
Mass (M_{\odot})	0.179 ± 0.014	
Radius (R_{\odot})	0.2139 ± 0.0041	
Luminosity (L_{\odot})	0.00441 ± 0.00013	
Temperature (K)	3216 ± 39	
Age (Gyr)	> 5	
	LHS 1140 b Parameters	LHS 1140 c Parameters
Period (days)	24.736959 ± 0.000080	3.777931 ± 0.000003
Radius (R_{\oplus})	1.727 ± 0.032	1.282 ± 0.024
Radius (r/R_{\star})	0.07390 ± 0.00008	0.05486 ± 0.00013
Mass (M_{\oplus})	6.98 ± 0.89	1.81 ± 0.39
Semi-major Axis (AU)	0.0936 ± 0.0024	0.02675 ± 0.00070
Semi-major Ratio (a/R_{\star})	95.34 ± 1.06	26.57 ± 0.05
Hill Sphere Radius (R_{\star})	3.23 ± 0.03	0.575 ± 0.012
Hill Sphere Radius (R_p)	43.76 ± 0.44	10.50 ± 0.11

As seen in the values above, LHS 1140 b has a very appealing combination of characteristics for hosting an exomoon: a large radius, large mass, and a low-mass host star lead LHS 1140 b to have a very large dynamical region for hosting exomoons. The size of the region that can dynamically host an exomoon is approximately given by the area of the Hill Sphere disc; in the case of LHS 1140 b, its Hill Sphere disc is a significant fraction - just over 10% - of that of the Earth, indicating that it has a large space to host a large moon.

LHS 1140 c, due to its smaller size and closer distance to LHS 1140, is a less appealing candidate to host an exomoon than its companion, but still boasts a large dynamical space compared to many other known terrestrial exoplanets. LHS 1140's Hill Sphere disc comes in at just over 3% the size of Earth's. Though this Hill Sphere disc is much smaller than that of LHS 1140 b, LHS 1140 c's Hill Sphere radius is still significantly larger than the planet's Roche Limit (which is approximately 2.2 planetary radii) at which a moon would be torn apart by tidal forces. This difference between Hill Sphere radius and Roche Limit radius indicates that the planet still has a large region where an exomoon could remain stable.

The LHS 1140 system boasts a very appealing arrangement for detecting exomoons; it is a local low-mass star with large planets - all very favorable conditions. Additionally, the fact that the system has been repeatedly observed and its parameters have been constrained to high precision makes analysis of data far easier, as there is less uncertainty regarding the validity of our results.

1.6. Format of Paper

Though exomoons are very difficult to detect with our current technological capabilities, the inarguable scientific benefits of exomoon discovery justify attempts at detection. In this paper, we will discuss our decision to use TESS data, outline the data collection techniques of TESS, provide background on the specific data set in which we search for exomoons, and describe our process for isolating transits, normalizing fluxes, estimating errors, and removing false outliers (Section 2). Then, we will describe the mechanics of our code, analyze LHS 1140 b and c, and characterize our success rate of moon characterization in simulated data, (Section 3). Finally, we will discuss the implications of our results, the limitations and assumptions of our method, and the potential application of our method to other planetary systems and data sets (Section 4).

2. METHODS

2.1. *Why TESS?*

The telescope used to collect our data for the LHS 1140 system is the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite, or TESS. When attempting to detect exoplanets and exomoons, TESS emerges as a strong candidate, as its express purpose is to discover transiting objects smaller than the size of Neptune (Ricker et al. 2010). TESS collects data for hundreds of thousands of stars, opening up an incredible number of potentially viable systems to analyze. Further, TESS frequently releases data to the public, and its data are very easy to interact with. Additionally, TESS’ rapid data collection cadence of either 20 seconds or 120 seconds enables analysis of shorter time-scale phenomena and promotes higher precision analysis compared to other space telescopes. Finally, TESS does a lot of data reduction work behind the scenes, including the nontrivial steps of background subtraction and normalization for stellar fluctuations (Ricker et al. 2010). Considering that the TESS data reduction process is done with the express purpose of preserving transit events, we do not have much concern that this data reduction process will erase traces of a potential exomoon transit.

Altogether, TESS provided the best combination of data accessibility, data quality, and breadth of objects to analyze out of the available telescopes, and was therefore our top choice to work with.

2.2. *TESS Data Collection*

TESS takes observations in the wavelength range 600-1000 nm, which corresponds to long-wavelength optical and near infrared light (Ricker et al. 2010). This range is optimal for our purposes, since small transiting objects are more easily detected around small stars, which are cool and red. The telescope is intended to be limited to an apparent magnitude of 13, but is still able to gather useful data on fainter M-dwarfs because they are so small (Ricker et al. 2010). This fact is crucial to our analysis of LHS 1140, as its apparent magnitude is 14 in the TESS band, but it is a faint M-dwarf (Ment et al. 2019). TESS takes a continuous stream of images with an exposure time of 2 sec, and then compiles these images to produce an effective exposure rate of either 20 seconds or 120 seconds. Then, once every 13.7 days, TESS has to pause observations for a few hours to downlink data to Earth (Ricker et al. 2010). Upon reception at Earth, the data is run through a data reduction pipeline based on software that was developed for the Kepler mission, which calibrates and normalizes the data so that it is ready to be analyzed (Ricker et al. 2010). This data reduction makes TESS data incredibly easy to work with and has made our data analysis in search of exomoons far easier than it may have been with other telescopes.

2.3. *Our Data Set*

Our flux data for LHS 1140 spans from 09/23/20 to 10/20/20 at a 20 second cadence, and contains 1 transit event of LHS 1140 b and 6 transit events of LHS 1140 c. It is publicly available, and we accessed it through the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST). Our observations come from the 30th sector of TESS, though there were also other observations done during the 3rd sector of TESS, which were analyzed by Lillo-Box et al. (2020). We use the presearch data-conditioning simple aperture photometry (PSDCSAP) detrending of the data, which normalizes the data for stellar-induced variations in flux and for background sources (Lillo-Box et al. 2020). This data has a large gap in it, as a result of downlinking data to Earth. Unfortunately, this gap happens to occur during an expected transit of LHS 1140 c, which reduces the number of available events for us to view. The data also cuts off slightly earlier than documented, causing us to miss out on data of an additional transit of LHS 1140 b by just a few hours.

These data were requested by George Ricker et. al, who analyzed similar TESS data from sector three two years prior in Lillo-Box et al. (2020). In this analysis, they found that all transit events of LHS 1140 c were compatible with the assumption of 0 transit timing variations up to a significance of 2σ . An exomoon would generate transit timing variations due to its gravitational effects on the planet, so this result suggests a lack of an exomoon around LHS 1140 c, a conclusion which we will support later in this project.

It is worth noting that searching for transit timing variations is a perfectly viable strategy for detecting exomoons; in the case of LHS 1140 b, an exomoon orbiting at half of its Hill Sphere radius with the same radius ratio as the moon to the earth would cause transit timing variations of up to 2.5 minutes. Detecting these small variations in transit timing is similarly difficult to trying to detect the exomoon’s transit itself, whose depth would be roughly 484 ppm in the scenario described above. In this project, we will focus only on attempting to directly detect a potential exomoon’s transit.

2.4. Isolating Transits within Data Set

267
268
269
270
271
272
273
274
275
276
277
278
279

As described above, our full data set spans nearly a month and contains 7 transit events. Consequently, it is a non-trivial process to locate each individual event. Thankfully, this process was made far simpler by the highly precise estimates of LHS 1140’s system parameters obtained by [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#). This research is able to provide a reference transit of LHS 1140 b which occurred at $2456915.71154 \pm 0.00004$ BJD. It was also able to constrain the orbital period to 24.736959 ± 0.00004 days. Due to these precise estimations, transit isolation became quite simple; we simply had to add scalar multiples of the orbital period onto the reference transit time until we reached the epoch of our data set. Due to the very small error bars, we located the desired events within errors of just a few minutes. We then centralize these transit events to $t = 0$, and are left to decide how much of the pre-transit and post-transit data to leave. For this project, we chose to leave 2 transit-lengths on both sides of the transit, as this choice leaves us plenty of data to normalize our flux but doesn’t expose us to longer-term variations in the data that may have managed to survive the data-reduction process.

We expected to locate two transits of LHS 1140 b in our data set, but only were able to isolate one:

Figure 3. We were able to isolate a clear transit, seen in the panel above. Unfortunately, since the reported conclusion of observations was later than the actual conclusion of observations, we missed a second transit of LHS 1140 b by a few hours.

280
281
282
283
284

We were also able to isolate the 6 transits of LHS 1140 c, again due to the precise estimates of [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#). They were able to provide a reference transit which occurred on $2458226.843169 \pm 0.000026$ BJD. They were also able to constrain the period to 3.777931 ± 0.000003 days. Applying the same strategy as above, adding scalar multiples of the orbital period to the reference transit until entering the epoch of the data, we are able to estimate the time of each of the 6 transits of LHS 1140 c. After doing so, we can isolate the following six events:

Figure 4. We have successfully isolated all 6 transit events. Note the shallow transit depth relative to LHS 1140 b’s transit; due to its smaller radius, its transits produce a far weaker signal than LHS 1140 b.

285 After isolating the transit events within the data set, the next steps to take are normalizing the flux, estimating the
 286 error of the data, and cutting out physically unreasonable outliers. Note that these steps have already been taken on
 287 the transit events displayed above. Let us briefly discuss the logistics of these processes.

288 2.5. Normalizing Flux, Estimating Error, and Clipping Outliers

289 Altering the flux data from an absolute photon count to a relative measurement and estimating the error of the data
 290 are two of the most crucial steps taken before analyzing transit events. Small differences in either step can significantly
 291 alter one’s analysis of the data.

292 When normalizing flux, one attempts to convert the data from a raw number of photons received to a flux percentage
 293 relative to the star’s pre- or post- transit state. Consequently, normalization of flux directly depends on estimating
 294 the star’s flux outside of the transit. To make this estimate, we simply averaged the median flux values of the first
 295 100 data points and the last 100 points after verifying that all 200 points were comfortably outside of the transit
 296 event. Then, we divided the entire data-set by this average value of non-transit flux to obtain a relative measure of
 297 flux instead of an absolute measure. This process is crucial to our research as it allows us to use the BATMAN transit
 298 package created by [Kreidberg \(2015\)](#), which works in terms of relative flux.

299 A correct estimation of error is crucial to the rest of our process, as our process is based upon χ^2 fitting, and χ^2 values
 300 directly depend upon error estimation. We took a similar approach to estimating error as we did for normalizing flux;
 301 we simply averaged the standard deviation of the first and last 100 points of the data set. This method yielded very
 302 similar estimations of error (within $\pm 5\%$) for each transit event, indicating that it produces consistent and reliable
 303 results. These observed errors were, on average, 6% higher than those estimated by the TESS data product, indicating
 304 that may be some minor external error sources that TESS is failing to consider. Both error values hovered in the range
 305 of 5 or 6 parts per thousand. Note that this error is roughly 100 times worse precision than the theoretical limit of
 306 TESS.

After normalizing flux and estimating error, we noticed that there were many positive outliers that strayed away from the rest of the data by an unusual amount. Since all of these severe outliers were positive, we concluded that they were either as a result of cosmic rays, stellar flares, or data collection anomalies. Consequently, we decided to clip out any outliers that strayed from the rest of the data by more than 3σ . After doing so, we can compare our original data to our outlier-adjusted data:

Figure 5. In the left panel, we can see the untouched normalized data. In the right panel, we can see the data after we omit significant outliers. We observe that we have only omitted positive outliers, which indicates that 3σ was not too shallow of a cut-off.

Now, we have successfully standardized all transit events to the same format, omitted physically unreasonable outliers, and obtained all necessary parameters to begin analysis.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Mechanics of Our Code

The purpose of our code is to analyze the data of an exoplanet transit event and decide whether or not there is evidence for a secondary moon transit. To do so, we need to generate transit events based on the parameters of a planetary system. Conveniently, there exists a very well-documented and easily accessible code by Batman, called BATMAN, created expressly for purpose. As inputs, BATMAN requires the time of central transit, orbital period, exoplanet radius, semi-major axis, orbital eccentricity, the longitude of periastron, and the limb-darkening parameters (Kreidberg 2015). Upon inputting these parameters, BATMAN generates a transit event. Note that due to our choice to work with normalized flux, combining transit-event models is quite easy. Modeling flux received for a joint exoplanet-exomoon transit can simply be given adding the model of an isolated planet transit with that of an isolated moon transit and subtracting 1 to re-normalize the data:

$$F_{Transit} = F_{planet} + F_{moon} - 1 \quad (6)$$

Then, we are able to evaluate the quality of the transit model's fit by calculating the χ^2 value, where:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(y(x_i) - F_{Transit}(x_i))^2}{\sigma^2} \quad (7)$$

The χ^2 metric tells us how well our model fits the data, as lower values indicate that the model is closer to the observed values. Therefore, by leaving some of BATMAN's parameters free, we can use a χ^2 minimizer to traverse the free-parameter space and locate optimal parameter values. First, we generate an optimal χ^2 fit for a lone-planetary

333 model, holding all parameters constant except planetary radius (obtaining the constant values from [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#)).
 334 Then, we generate an optimal χ^2 fit for a concurrent exomoon and exoplanet transit model, allowing exoplanet radius,
 335 exomoon radius, and transit timing offset to remain free.

336 Unfortunately, our χ^2 minimizer struggled to traverse the 3-parameter (moon radius, planet radius, and time offset)
 337 space of the moon model, and was unable to consistently estimate transit time-offset values in simulated data. So, to
 338 assist in the code’s traversal of the parameter space, we wrote a method that iterates over all dynamically possible
 339 time-offset values (see [Section 1.4](#) for an explanation of how these values were calculated) and submits these time-offset
 340 values as a prior for our χ^2 minimizer. Then, we accepted the time-offset prior that generated to the lowest χ^2 value,
 341 as long as this time-offset value corresponded to a non-negative predicted exomoon radius (negative radii are allowed
 342 in BATMAN, and are also allowed in our χ^2 minimizer, so we filter out these unrealistic predictions manually).

343 The difference between the χ^2 values of our two models corresponds to a probability of the the null-hypothesis, or
 344 the probability that randomly occurring data would generate the observed difference in quality of fit between our two
 345 models. Based on this p value, we can choose to accept or reject the moon model. For this project, we took a p value
 346 of 0.003 to indicate statistical significance, which corresponds to a significance of 3σ . If our p value fell below 0.003,
 347 we would be able to conclude that the exomoon model represented a significantly better fit than the planet model,
 348 and that we had detected evidence for a transiting exomoon.

349 The segment of our code described above allows us to decide whether or not there is evidence for an exomoon transit
 350 within the data. Independent of its conclusion, though, it is also a worthwhile endeavor, to consider what size exomoon
 351 could go undetected in the transit as a result of the data noise.

352 So, in an attempt to constrain the maximum radius of a moon that may be hidden, we wrote a code that iterates
 353 through moons of different sizes (from 1% to 100% of the planet’s radius), calculating the χ^2 for the model at all
 354 possible time-offset values. By comparing the best χ^2 for each tested moon radius to the χ^2 of the planet model, we
 355 could determine at what exomoon radius the lone-planet model would obtain a statistically significant χ^2 improvement
 356 compared to the exomoon model at any possible time-offset value. Past this moon radius, there is no possible time-offset
 357 at which the moon model is indistinguishable from the lone-planet model to 3σ .

358 Effectively, this segment of the code answers the question: what is the biggest possible moon that we could hide in
 359 the data noise at which the planet model and the moon model would still be statistically indistinguishable? Then,
 360 based on this maximum moon radius, we can claim with a confidence of 3σ that moons greater than this maximum
 361 radius would have been visible in our transit event. Note that it is dynamically possible, though unlikely in most cases,
 362 for the moon to be hidden in front of the planet, in which case our estimation of maximum hidden moon radius would
 363 be inaccurate. The probability of such an orientation is discussed in detail in [Section 1.3](#).

364 These two outputs are the main takeaways of our code. From top to bottom, our process begins with an input of
 365 transit data and concludes with a decision of whether there is evidence of a moon transit in the data and what the
 366 maximum radius of an moon hidden in the data noise could be.

367 3.2. Analysis of LHS 1140 b Transit

368 As described above, the first step of our data analysis process is to fit a lone-planetary transit model to the data.
 369 This fit yielded an estimate of the radius of LHS 1140 b of $R_p = (0.0758 \pm 0.0019)R_\star$. This value is very similar to the
 370 value estimated by [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#) of $(0.07390 \pm 0.00008)R_\star$, indicating that our fitting process is effective. This
 371 fit returned a χ^2 value of 1743.45, which we will later use to compare this model with the transiting exomoon model.
 372 Also note that this value is within 2% of the size of our data set, indicating that, generally, this model is a good fit.

373 Then, to determine if there is evidence of a moon in this transit, we fit our joint exoplanet and exomoon transit
 374 model to the data. This fit yields the following results:

375

Table 2: LHS 1140 b Exoplanet and Exomoon Model Results			
R_p/R_\star	R_m/R_\star	Time Offset (min)	χ^2
0.0721 ± 0.0038	0.025 ± 0.010	23.1 ± 7.5	1741.91

376 The $\Delta\chi^2$ between the two models comes out to be 1.54, which corresponds to $p = 0.672$, leading us to conclude that
 377 there is no evidence for an exomoon based on this transit event. Based on the noise for this transit, any moons with
 378 radius greater than $0.51R_p$ would have been detected, to a significance of 3σ .

379 We can plot both models and their residuals to visually interpret the quality of the fit. First, let us take a look at
 380 our lone-planetary model.

Figure 6. Visually, the lone-planet model appears to be a good fit to the data. The residuals, which appear to be centered at 0 across all time values, support this conclusion.

381 Now, we can compare this fit to that of our moon model:

Figure 7. The fit and residuals of our joint exomoon and exoplanet transit model with our binned data. Notice the small secondary flux drop in the left figure as the possible exomoon passes in front of the star 23.1 minutes after the planet does. Note that the residuals appear largely identical to those of the lone-planet model.

382 Visually, the fits and residuals are nearly indistinguishable; this intuitive analysis matches the statistically indistin-
 383 guishable χ^2 comparison that we saw above.

3.3. Analysis of LHS 1140 c Transits

Within our TESS data set of LHS 1140, there were 6 transits of LHS 1140 c. After isolating these events, we first fit the lone-planetary model to the data, yielding the following radius estimates for each transit:

Transit Number	R_p/R_\star	Transit Number	R_p/R_\star
1	0.0542 ± 0.0035	4	0.0610 ± 0.0031
2	0.0531 ± 0.0035	5	0.0471 ± 0.0039
3	0.0506 ± 0.0037	6	0.0516 ± 0.0035

These radius estimations are similar to that of [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#), indicating that our lone-planetary model is working as intended.

Now, let us run our moon model to generate our $\Delta\chi^2$ values and determine whether or not there is evidence of an exomoon transit around LHS 1140 c.

Transit Number	R_p/R_\star	R_m/R_\star	Time Offset (min)	$\Delta\chi^2$	P Value
1	0.0502 ± 0.0064	0.023 ± 0.014	14.7 ± 6.3	0.84	0.841
2	0.0508 ± 0.0049	0.019 ± 0.013	23.7 ± 8.0	0.55	0.907
3	0.0459 ± 0.0064	0.024 ± 0.012	-17.7 ± 5.8	1.21	0.752
4	0.0576 ± 0.0047	0.024 ± 0.011	-21.7 ± 5.8	1.58	0.664
5	0.032 ± 0.011	0.0376 ± 0.0094	12.2 ± 2.9	3.69	0.297
6	0.0440 ± 0.0074	0.030 ± 0.011	-14.1 ± 4.1	2.14	0.545

The $\Delta\chi^2$ value corresponding to a significance of $p = 0.05$ is 7.81 and 13.93 for $p = 0.003$. Without even probing each result individually, none of our $\Delta\chi^2$ values reach these values, so we can conclude that there is no statistical evidence for an exomoon around LHS 1140 c based on this transit data. Despite this null result, Let us further investigate the individual results displayed in the table above.

In transits 3, 5, and 6, the χ^2 minimizer generates exomoons with radius greater than half that of LHS 1140 c and decreases the expected planet radius to a value far lower than its tightly constrained real-life value. Upon seeing this result, we began to question whether planet radius should remain a free parameter within our moon model fitting; if the minimizer is taking advantage of this free parameter to generate unrealistic fits, perhaps it would be best to hold this parameter constant. So, we attempted the same moon model fit, except this time holding the radius of the planet constant, at the value determined by [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#).

Doing so, we returned the following results:

Transit Number	R_m/R_\star	Time Offset (min)	$\Delta\chi^2$	P Value
1	0.010 ± 0.020	11 ± 23	0.04	0.999
2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
4	0.0287 ± 0.0066	-18.7 ± 4.4	1.46	0.692
5	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
6	0.005 ± 0.033	-14 ± 66	0.01	0.999

In transits 1, 2, 3, 5, and 6 the moon model was unable to generate any physically plausible results, so it either threw an error (as in transits 2, 3, and 5), or sent the radius of the moon to nearly 0 (as in transits 1 and 6).

This leaves us with only one interesting model fit, which is for transit 4. Consequently, let us take a look at the fit and residuals for both models of this particular event. We'll plot the constant-planet-radius moon model, since its radius has been so well constrained in current literature (though the radius estimate in the free-planet-radius model was quite reasonable):

Figure 8. We can see the fits and residuals for the lone-planet model and the moon transit model of the fourth LHS 1140 c transit event. In the bottom left panel, notice the small secondary dip in the projected flux as a result of the expected exomoon transit.

Both fits plausibly match the data, and it is difficult to notice a difference in the residuals. Our $\Delta\chi^2$ value of 1.46, which corresponds to $p = 0.692$, supports the conclusion that these two models are indistinguishable.

Though we do not observe any evidence of an exomoon in any of our six transit events of LHS 1140 c, we are still able to bound the maximum possible radius of a moon that may be going undetected within the noise of the data. The transit event which provided the best bound on the maximum possible exomoon radius was the third, which revealed to a significance of $p = 0.003$ or 3σ that if LHS 1140 c had an exomoon of radius greater than 0.66 times its own, we would have detected it in this data.

3.4. Expected Results with Different Quality Data

While our results with TESS data provide unique constraints on the LHS 1140 system, these constraints could be significantly improved with better quality data. Across all 7 transit events, our average data noise was approximately $\sigma = 0.005$, or 5 parts per thousand. Let us discuss our code's ability to recover a system's parameters if we brought this error down to 1 part per thousand, or $\sigma = 0.001$. Note that this value is well within the theoretical limit of TESS, which is 50 parts per million.

We will evaluate our code’s effectiveness on simulated data for LHS 1140 b, since it is the more likely candidate of the two planets to host an exomoon due to its larger Hill Sphere.

To do so, we will simulate four exoplanet and exomoon transits of the LHS 1140 b system. In each case, we will set the exomoon radius to planet radius to that of the earth-moon system, with $R_m/R_\oplus = 0.27$, and we will set the error to $\sigma = 0.001$. We will investigate four different transit orientations, similar to those described in Section 1.4. The first orientation will be two distinct transit events, where the exomoon transit occurs 1.5 times the transit time duration before the exoplanet transit. The second and third will represent a 50% transit overlap and 80% transit overlap, respectively. Finally, the fourth will represent completely overlapping transit events, where the exoplanet transit hides the exomoon transit, leaving the exomoon is undetectable from our perspective. Intuitively, we would expect the code to struggle to identify moons in the cases where there is more transit overlap. Let us see if this is the case.

Table 6: Simulated LHS 1140 b Transit Results

Transit Number and Orientation	R_m/R_p (0.27)	Time Offset	$\Delta\chi^2$	Sig. to 3σ ?
1 (Distinct Transits)	0.266 ± 0.018	-1.531 ± 0.017 (set to be -1.5)	82.67	✓
2 (50% Transit Overlap)	0.269 ± 0.020	-0.499 ± 0.016 (set to be -0.5)	74.06	✓
3 (80% Transit Overlap)	0.254 ± 0.033	-0.203 ± 0.018 (set to be -0.2)	29.01	✓
4 (100% Transit Overlap)	0.193 ± 0.078	0.087 ± 0.029 (set to be 0)	2.66	×

These results demonstrate that our code is able to accurately recover the parameters of an exomoon within a wide variety of transit orientations for LHS 1140 b when the data noise is reduced to 1 part per thousand. The only exception, of course, is when the exomoon transit is hidden in front of or behind the exoplanet’s; in this case, the code is unable to produce a good fit for the joint exomoon and exoplanet transit model and returns a negative result. Notice the decreasing values of $\Delta\chi^2$ as the transit events coincide more; this result aligns with our intuition that an exomoon is easier to detect when its transit event is farther separated from the exoplanet’s.

The predicted parameters closely match their average values in each case where the code claims to have detected an exomoon; we know that the real value of R_m/R_p in this simulation is 0.27, and the code generates similar values to this in each of the first three cases. It also generates accurate estimates of the timing offset within a few minutes. While it generates inaccurate parameters in the hidden moon transit case, it acknowledges that the corresponding fit does not achieve statistical significance compared to the lone-planetary model.

We can observe the accuracy of these projections by comparing the transit event that they generate to the actual simulated transit:

Figure 9. In each simulated transit, the model’s prediction fits tightly to the real event, indicating that our code is successfully identifying the parameters of this system. Notice that in the 100% Overlap transit event, the model predicts a visible exomoon despite it actually being invisible to us. This prediction is statistically indistinguishable from the lone-planetary model, and therefore is not concerning.

448

We are also able to constrain the moon radius in each of these simulated transits:

Transit Number and Orientation	Maximum R_m/R_p	Sig. to 3σ ?
1 (Distinct Transits)	0.41	✓
2 (50% Transit Overlap)	0.36	✓
3 (80% Transit Overlap)	0.34	✓
4 (100% Transit Overlap)	0.19	✓

449

450

Note that as the amount of transit overlap increases, the bound on the radius decreases, until it becomes incorrect at 100% overlap; in this case, we know that the correct value of R_m/R_p is 0.27, but our code places the maximum value at 0.19. Even though our code claims that this bound is significant to 3σ , it is clearly incorrect, and it reveals one of the main limitations of our code; our transit analysis is inaccurate if the exomoon is hidden in front of or behind the exoplanet. For LHS 1140 b, the probability of this transit orientation is just $p = 0.052$ (as calculated in [Section 1.3](#)), so with analysis of multiple transit events, we could effectively eliminate this concern.

456

Interestingly, as already discussed, the 100% transit overlap case would appear the same from our perspective as a system with no exomoon at all; consequently, our bound on maximum moon radius of 0.19 planetary radii is the same bound as what we would expect to place on a system with no exomoon. Therefore, if our data noise were reduced to $\sigma = 0.001$, we could to place constraints on this system for exomoons with a smaller radius ratio than our own moon.

460

4. DISCUSSION

461

4.1. Implications of Results for LHS 1140 System

462

We have determined to a significance of 3σ that there are no transiting exomoons around LHS 1140 b with radius greater than 0.51 planetary radii or around LHS 1140 c with radius greater than 0.66 planetary radii. We observe no evidence of a transiting exomoon in any of the 7 events analyzed, even at a very low significance level. Let us discuss the implications of these findings on the LHS 1140 system as a whole.

466

In the attempt to identify habitable exomoons or exoplanets, we look for systems which exhibit similarities to Earth. In the case of LHS 1140 b, whose radius is 1.73 times that of Earth according to [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#), we claim to a significance of 3σ that there are no moons with radius greater than .88 Earth radii. Similarly, for LHS 1140 c, whose

468

radius as determined by [Ment et al. \(2019\)](#) is 1.28 Earth radii, we find that there are no moons greater 0.85 Earth radii. Note that the similarity of these bounds makes sense, as they are dependent on the TESS data noise. It remains statistically uncertain, however, if there are any satellites smaller than these bounds within the system. Consequently, an object of near-earth size, with a radius of 0.88 Earth radii or less, may be lying undetected in the data noise. This situation would be surprising considering our code’s performance on simulated data, but remains a statistical possibility nonetheless. Since near-earth sized objects could be going undetected, we can not rule out the possibility of a habitable, earth-like exomoon existing in this system; instead, we only claim that it is unlikely as we would expect that there would be some evidence of its presence in our analysis.

In fact, one could argue that the bound that we have placed on these exoplanets’ satellites is not even a bound on their potential exomoons; instead, our bounds are in the domain of binary planets. If either exoplanet had a satellite with a radius at our upper bound that existed at the planet’s Hill Sphere radius, the center of mass of the system would exist outside of the body of the exoplanet, and therefore the system would be categorized as a binary planet system. To be clear, we are not suggesting that either planet is a binary planet, we are only acknowledging that it could be a possibility according to the upper bound on satellite radius that we derived from analyzing these transit events.

Since the data we analyzed only allowed us to place bounds in the regime of binary planets, we can not provide much insight into the possibility of the moon obliquity stabilization effect as described by [Kane \(2017\)](#). Moons could certainly still exist around either exoplanet that exert this effect.

In the solar system, the only case of a large moon occurring around a terrestrial planet is Earth’s, which was created via collision. A lack of large terrestrial exomoons in the LHS 1140 system may indicate that there have not been many interactions between planet-sized objects that would lead to large exomoon captures or collisions, which could suggest that this stellar system has achieved a relatively stable state.

4.2. *Limitations and Assumptions*

There are a few noteworthy limitations and assumptions of our research that should be addressed. The first, which has been referenced numerous times already, is the fact that exomoons directly aligned in front of their exoplanet from our perspective would be undetectable in transit data. This alignment could lead to false negatives, which is why it is best to observe multiple transit events before drawing conclusions about exomoon presence. In our case, since we only have one transit event for LHS 1140 b within our data set, we can not be certain that our lack of evidence of an exomoon stems from an actual lack of an exomoon; there is a possibility that there is an exomoon around LHS 1140 b which happened to be inconveniently aligned during the transit event that we analyzed. If an exomoon does exist around LHS 1140 b, we would estimate its probability of inconvenient alignment to be roughly 5.2%, meaning that it would be best to analyze another LHS 1140 b transit event so that we can be more sure that this unfavorable alignment did not occur. This limitation is far less prevalent in our conclusion about LHS 1140 c, as we analyzed six separate transit events. The chance of undetectable moon alignment in all six events is nearly zero (on the order of 1 in a million) so we can have far more confidence in our null result.

Another limitation of our process is its dependence on previously existing data. In order to run our code, we need to have well constrained estimates of star mass, exoplanet mass, radius, orbital distance, orbital period, and inclination. This dependence on previous data reduces the number of planetary systems that we are able to analyze, and exposes us to the possibility of drawing inaccurate conclusions if the data that we are referencing on is inaccurate.

Additionally, while our process is effective at drawing conclusions regarding exomoon presence in a transit event, the only constraint that we can place on a possible exomoon’s physical parameters is its radius. We would be unable to infer its orbital period, distance, mass, or density. In order to begin to constrain these parameters, we would need to analyze the system with a larger data set containing a multitude transit events to begin search for transit timing variations and transit duration variations. These differences between transits would allow us to begin to constrain these other crucial exomoon parameters. Had we detected an exomoon in these transit events of LHS 1140, this is the next step that we would have taken.

Further, a fundamental assumption of our process is that the exomoon is stationary in its orbit during the transit event. This assumption causes the duration of our exomoon and exoplanet transits to be equal, which would not be the case in reality. This negative effect of this assumption is negligible; we would not expect the exomoon to move significantly during the few hours that we are analyzing. Regardless, adjusting for this assumption, perhaps by adding

an additional free parameter in our moon model for the moon’s relative velocity, may be a worthwhile endeavor in the future.

Finally, a limiting assumption of our process was the limb-darkening parameters of our system. Limb-darkening, or the rate at which the light emitted by a star falls off from its center, has a significant impact on the appearance of a transit event. For this project, we assumed quadratic limb-darkening at the default value suggested by [Kreidberg \(2015\)](#), which was confirmed to be physically reasonable for a star at the temperature of LHS 1140 by [Kipping \(2013\)](#). We assumed this constant value after attempting to allow limb-darkening parameters to remain free variables in our models and finding that they dominated the fits and drowned out the other, more important, systemic parameters. Consequently, we were forced to leave these values constant. Our assumed limb-darkening parameters, however, may not be accurate; estimating limb-darkening is a very difficult task and there is no consensus optimal strategy for doing so.

4.3. Future Directions

There are many possible directions to continue with this project. As addressed above, there are limitations and imperfections within our research process that could be adjusted. We could also try to analyze other planetary systems with large dynamical space to host exomoons to broaden the scope of our attempt at exomoon detection. An even bigger pivot could be taken to attempt using data from other telescopes; perhaps Kepler or JWST data may yield more fruitful results.

4.3.1. Other Planetary Systems

With the central goal of our research being the first detection of a terrestrial exomoon, the breadth of our search has an immense impact on our chance of success. Having only probed one stellar system, it is unsurprising that we did not achieve this overarching goal. It follows, then, that one of our next steps should be to broaden our search. Some possible targets for investigation in the future include the Trappist 1 system or Isolated Planetary-mass Objects (IPMOs), as suggested by [Limbach et al. \(2021\)](#).

The Trappist-1 system is an appealing target due to its low-mass host star, large planets, and large number of exoplanets to check for exomoons. It also boasts a wide variety of observations to analyze, as it has been a system of interest for many years. Probing this system would be very enticing if [Kane \(2017\)](#) had not already conducted exomoon analysis on Trappist-1 in search of transit timing variations and transit depth variations and concluded that exomoons are unlikely to be present. Considering that this system has already been probed for exomoons and has been deemed unlikely to be hosting any, we may be better off setting our sights on other systems.

In order to discover the first terrestrial exomoon, many more systems than just Trappist-1 and LHS 1140 will need to be investigated. It makes the most sense to probe systems with large dynamical spaces for hosting exomoons. To do so, we want to investigate large exoplanets on long orbital periods around small stars. To be more mathematical about these preferences, the Hill Sphere radius scales roughly as $a * R_p^{1/3} * R_\star^{-1/3}$. By scanning through the NASA Exoplanet archive for the planets which maximize this quantity, we might be able to develop a catalog of target exoplanets for our exomoon hunt as we look forward.

An interesting possibility for terrestrial exomoon detection was proposed by [Limbach et al. \(2021\)](#), which is probing Isolated Planetary-mass Objects for exomoons. Around these objects, transiting moons are expected to be common, given that close-orbiting moons have a high geometric transit probability and are expected to be a common outcome of giant planet formation ([Limbach et al. 2021](#)). Some of the most appealing candidates, according to this research, include WISE 0855 (which will be observed by JWST in the near future), 2MASS J0249–0557c, WISE J174102.78–464225.5, or SIMP J013656.5+093347, as an exomoon around these IPMOs may be detectable with JWST to 5σ with radius as small as 0.25 Earth radii ([Limbach et al. 2021](#)).

4.3.2. Other Telescopes

Our results presented in [Section 3.4](#) highlight the improvement in results that we might expect if we analyze data with an improved signal-to-noise ratio (at a part in a thousand instead of five parts per thousand). The most fruitful source of improved data is, unsurprisingly, the JWST. According to [Limbach et al. \(2021\)](#), JWST would be able to achieve data noise in the realm of 50 parts-per-million around the most favorable IPMOs, which is about 20 times better signal-to-noise than the optimistic analysis conducted in ([Section 3.4](#)). It is also worth noting that JWST is

567 expected to be able to reach a precision of 5 parts per million in some observations - a full thousand times better
 568 than the data we analyzed in this project. With this incredible data quality, our research process would be able to
 569 draw incredibly powerful conclusions about the presence of exomoons around celestial objects, especially these IPMOs.
 570 With JWST observations of WISE 0855 coming out in the near future, this dream may have a chance of manifesting
 571 into reality.

572 While the JWST would provide incredible capability to detect individual exomoon transit events, its sparse obser-
 573 vation time would make recurring observations of a single exomoon candidate nearly impossible. Without multiple
 574 transit events, it would be impossible to observe transit timing variations and transit duration variations, and conse-
 575 quently impossible to constrain the moon’s mass, density, orbital distance, or orbital period. Kepler data, according
 576 to Kipping (2014) is the best for this purpose, as it boasts high quality signal-to-noise, a long baseline of observations,
 577 and a focus on low-mass objects. Perhaps, then, the best chance of detecting and characterizing an exomoon involves
 578 transit analysis using JWST data in the same manner as what we have done here, followed by a search for transit
 579 timing variations or transit duration variations using Kepler data.

580 5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

581 First, I would like to acknowledge my research advisor, Dr. David Charbonneau, for his immense support throughout
 582 this project. Without his expertise, kindness, and consistent willingness to help, this project would not have been
 583 possible.

584 Additionally, I would like to thank Patrick Tamburo for his thoughtful advice on how I could improve both my
 585 research process and my paper.

586 I would also like to thank my peers, Arielle Frommer and Caleb Painter, for sharing their expertise in analyzing
 587 transit data and helping me to interact with raw TESS data.

588 Next, I would like to acknowledge Professor Xingang Chen for helping me to establish a timeline for this project
 589 and for emphasizing the importance of collaboration in research.

590 Finally, I would like to thank Shreyas Vissapragada, Samuel Yee, Collin Cherubim, and Jea Adams for offering
 591 support in my attempt to analyze JWST data for this project. Though JWST data did not end up becoming part of
 592 this project, I am very appreciative of their willingness to support my research.

593 This paper includes data collected with the TESS mission, obtained from the MAST data archive at the Space
 594 Telescope Science Institute (STScI). Funding for the TESS mission is provided by the NASA Explorer Program.
 595 STScI is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS
 596 5-26555.

REFERENCES

- 597 Barr, A. C. 2016, *The Astronomical Review*, 12, 24,
 598 doi: [10.1080/21672857.2017.1279469](https://doi.org/10.1080/21672857.2017.1279469)
- 599 Benisty, M., Bae, J., Facchini, S., et al. 2021, *ApJL*, 916,
 600 L2, doi: [10.3847/2041-8213/ac0f83](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ac0f83)
- 601 Dobos, V., Charnoz, S., Pál, A., Roque-Bernard, A., &
 602 Szabó, G. M. 2021, *PASP*, 133, 094401,
 603 doi: [10.1088/1538-3873/abfe04](https://doi.org/10.1088/1538-3873/abfe04)
- 604 Gaia Collaboration, Brown, A. G. A., Vallenari, A., et al.
 605 2018, *A&A*, 616, A1, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/201833051](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833051)
- 606 Hartmann, W. K., & Davis, D. R. 1975, *Icarus*, 24, 504,
 607 doi: [10.1016/0019-1035\(75\)90070-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0019-1035(75)90070-6)
- 608 Heller, R., Williams, D., Kipping, D., et al. 2014,
 609 *Astrobiology*, 14, 798, doi: [10.1089/ast.2014.1147](https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2014.1147)
- 610 Kane, S. R. 2017, *ApJL*, 839, L19,
 611 doi: [10.3847/2041-8213/aa6bf2](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/aa6bf2)
- 612 Kipping, D., Bryson, S., Burke, C., et al. 2022, 54, 504.04
- 613 Kipping, D. M. 2009, *MNRAS*, 392, 181,
 614 doi: [10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13999.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2966.2008.13999.x)
- 615 —. 2013, *MNRAS*, 435, 2152, doi: [10.1093/mnras/stt1435](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stt1435)
- 616 —. 2014, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:1405.1455,
 617 doi: [10.48550/arXiv.1405.1455](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1405.1455)
- 618 Kreidberg, L. 2015, *PASP*, 127, 1161, doi: [10.1086/683602](https://doi.org/10.1086/683602)
- 619 Lillo-Box, J., Figueira, P., Leleu, A., et al. 2020, *A&A*, 642,
 620 A121, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202038922](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202038922)
- 621 Limbach, M. A., Vos, J. M., Winn, J. N., et al. 2021, *ApJL*,
 622 918, L25, doi: [10.3847/2041-8213/ac1e2d](https://doi.org/10.3847/2041-8213/ac1e2d)
- 623 Lunine, J. I., & Stevenson, D. J. 1982, *Icarus*, 52, 14,
 624 doi: [10.1016/0019-1035\(82\)90166-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0019-1035(82)90166-X)
- 625 Makarov, V. V., & Efroimsky, M. 2023, *A&A*, 672, A78,
 626 doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202245533](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202245533)
- 627 McCord, T. B. 1966, *AJ*, 71, 585, doi: [10.1086/109967](https://doi.org/10.1086/109967)

- 628 Ment, K., Dittmann, J. A., Astudillo-Defru, N., et al. 2019, 632 Venturini, J., Guilera, O. M., Haldemann, J., Ronco, M. P.,
629 AJ, 157, 32, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/aaf1b1](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/aaf1b1) 633 & Mordasini, C. 2020, A&A, 643, L1,
630 Ricker, G. R., Latham, D. W., Vanderspek, R. K., et al. 634 doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/202039141](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/202039141)
631 2010, 215, 450.06